

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR PHD GRADUATES AND PHD RESEARCHERS

1. Have you already participated in an MSCA ITN/DN project?

Scroll down menu: Yes/No

a. CONDITIONAL – if answer to Q1 is YES.

If yes, in how many projects?

Open field - Any number

b. CONDITIONAL – if answer to Q1 is YES.

Please list the projects you have participated in, along with your role in each project (up to 5 projects, starting with the most recent).

Project number	Acronym	Name of the Institution (in English)	Country	Your role in the project	If your role is "Other"
Scroll down menu	Scroll down menu	Open field	Scroll down menu	<i>Multiple choice:</i> - Early-Stage Researcher - Doctoral Candidate, - Supervisor - Coordinator - Principal Investigator - Project Manager - Other	
List up to 10 projects					

2. In which country do you currently work?

- Country: drop down menu

3. In which institution do you currently work?

- Institution: open field

4. In which role have you been most recently (or are currently) involved in a PhD programme?

A PhD researcher is one who is currently pursuing a PhD, whereas a PhD graduate is one who has already completed a PhD.

PI/Supervisor

- PhD graduate
- PhD researcher

5. Was your PhD funded by the MSCA programme (MSCA Innovative Training Networks /MSCA Doctoral Networks)?

Scroll down menu: Yes/No

a. CONDITIONAL – If answer is yes

Why did you decide to apply for MSCA funding? What motivated you to choose this programme over a national one?

- Prestige of the funding programme
- Funding/Resources
- International dimension
- Intersectoral collaboration opportunities
- Emphasis on interdisciplinary research
- Networking opportunities
- Bottom-up approach
- Career support
- PhD Programme reputation
- Chances of success
- EU dimension
- Diversity and inclusion
- Other

b. If “Other”, please specify.

Answer: Free text box

c. CONDITIONAL – If answer is no

What factors influenced your decision to choose a particular PhD program?

Please select up to 3 main reasons:

- Research topic
- Research team
- Supervisor
- Faculty reputation
- Country
- Prestige of the funding programme
- Prestige of the University
- EU dimension
- Funding/Resources
- Salary
- Working conditions
- Programme structure (training)
- Networking opportunities
- Mobility

- Programme size
- Career support
- Programme flexibility (courses outside core discipline)
- PhD Programme reputation
- Diversity and inclusion
- Other

d. If "Other", please specify.

Answer: Free text box

e. CONDITIONAL – if answer is no

Were you aware of the existence of the MSCA programme?

Drop down menu: Yes, No

6. How did you find your PhD position?

- University websites
- Euraxess
- FindaPhD.com
- PhDportal.com
- GradSchools.com
- ProFellow.com
- Academicpositions.com
- ResearchGate
- LinkedIn
- Friend's recommendation
- Supervisor's recommendation
- Email distribution
- Scientific journals
- Other (Free text box)

a. If "Other", please specify.

Answer: Free text box

7. When did you complete your PhD?

Drop down menu: Before 2016, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, Still ongoing.

8. Were you recruited by an academic or non-academic entity* during your PhD?

*(‘Academic sector’ means public or private higher education establishments awarding academic degrees, public or private non-profit research organisations and International European Research Organisations (IERO). ‘Non-academic sector’ means any socio-economic actor not included in the academic sector).

- Academic
- Non-academic

- Both
- Other (Free text box)

a. **CONDITIONAL** - If previous is **academic or other**.

Have you engaged with non-academic organisations as part of your PhD research?

Drop down menu: Yes, No, I don't know

b. **CONDITIONAL** – if previous is YES and answer to question 4 is B or C.

In which fields did you experience a positive impact stemming from your intersectoral experience and to what extent?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To no extent	I don't know
Research scope and methodology					
International collaborations					
Interdisciplinary research and collaborations					
Enhanced networking and communication capacities					
Career prospects / Enhanced employability & reputation					
Research funding					
New research and transferable skills and competences					
Innovation / Entrepreneurship					
Knowledge Transfer / Cross-fertilisation of ideas					
Increased integration of training and research activities					
Societal impact					
Economic impact					
Environmental impact					

Work culture					
Change of discipline					
Change of country					
Publication benefits					
IPR strategy development Access to resources					
Knowledge of the market					
Industry experience					
Sustainability					
Other					

c. If “Other”, please specify.

Answer: free-text box

d. CONDITIONAL – if answer to question 4 is B or C.

What were the biggest challenges you faced in working across sectors and to what extent?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To no extent	I don't know
Focus of the research project					
Supervision support					
Resource availability / funding challenges					
Personal adaptation					
Differences in work culture and expectations					
Administrative issues/Institutional support					
Adapting to different communication styles					
Academic isolation/integration (limited access to academic resources and support)					
Assessment and evaluation (different standards & expectations across sectors)					

Balancing industry demands with PhD research requirements					
Difficulty translating academic skills to industry-specific needs					
Publication difficulties					
Navigating intellectual property rights and confidentiality agreements					
Time management					
Other					

- e. If “Other”, please specify.
 Answer: free-text box

9. Intersectoral - In which sector do you work at the moment?

- Academic
- Non-academic
- I don't know

10. Would you consider your PhD project to be interdisciplinary*?

* **‘Interdisciplinarity’** means the integration of information, data, techniques, tools, perspectives, concepts or theories from two or more scientific disciplines. The term discipline refers to the first level of MSCA keywords.

Scroll down menu: Yes/No

- a. CONDITIONAL – if answer to question 6 is YES.

In which fields did you experience a positive impact stemming from your interdisciplinary experience and to what extent?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To no extent	I don't know
Research scope and methodology					
International collaborations					
Intersectoral collaborations					
Enhanced networking and communication capacities					

Career prospects / Enhanced employability & reputation					
Research funding					
Increased transferable skills and competences					
Innovation / Entrepreneurship					
Knowledge Transfer / Cross-fertilisation of ideas					
Increased integration of training and research activities					
Societal impact					
Economic impact					
Work culture					
Change of discipline					
Change of country					
Publications benefits					
IPR strategy development					
Access to resources					
Global perspectives					
Industry experience					
Sustainability					
Environmental impact					
Other					

b. If “Other”, please specify.

Answer: free-text box

c. CONDITIONAL – if answer to question 6 is YES.

What were the biggest challenges you faced in working across disciplines and to what extent?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To no extent	I don't know
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Focus of the research project					
Supervision support					
Resource availability / funding challenges					
Personal adaptation					
Differences in work culture and expectations					
Administrative issues/Institutional support					
Adapting to different communication styles					
Academic isolation/integration (limited access to academic resources and support)					
Assessment and evaluation (different standards & expectations across disciplines)					
Training /course requirements (balancing coursework from different disciplines, which may have conflicting requirements and schedules)					
Publication difficulties					
Complications related to intellectual property rights					
Time management					
Other					

- d. If "Other", please specify.
 Answer: free-text box

11. Did you gain international experience during your PhD research?

Scroll down menu: Yes/No

- a. CONDITIONAL question – if answer to question 7 is YES.

In which fields did you experience a positive impact stemming from your international experience and to what extent?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To no extent	I don't know
Research scope and methodology					
Intersectoral collaborations					
Interdisciplinary collaborations					
Enhanced networking and communication capacities					
Career prospects / Enhanced employability & reputation					
Research funding					
Increased transferable skills and competences					
Innovation / Entrepreneurship					
Knowledge Transfer / Cross-fertilisation of ideas					
Increased integration of training and research activities					
Societal impact					
Economic impact					
Work culture					
Change of discipline					
Change of country					
Publications benefits					
IPR strategy development					
Access to resources					
Global perspectives					
Industry experience					
Sustainability					

Environmental impact					
Other					

b. If “Other”, please specify.

Answer: free-text box

c. If answer to question 7 is YES. What were the biggest challenges you faced working in an international environment and to what extent?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To no extent	I don't know
Focus of the research project					
Supervision support					
Resource availability / funding challenges					
Personal adaptation					
Differences in work culture and expectations					
Administrative issues/Institutional support					
Adapting to different communication styles					
Academic isolation/integration (limited access to academic resources and support)					
Assessment and evaluation (different standards & expectations across countries)					
Recognition of Qualifications					
Publication difficulties					
Complications related to intellectual property rights					
Time management					
Language barriers					
Other					

d. If “Other”, please specify.

Answer: free-text box

12. CONDITIONAL – if answer to any of the “I” questions is YES.

What skills did you gain through your intersectoral, international and interdisciplinary collaboration that you find valuable?

	Intersectoral	International	Interdisciplinary
	Technical skills	Technical skills	Technical skills
	Social skills	Social skills	Social skills
	Intercultural skills	Intercultural skills	Intercultural skills
	Collaborative skills	Collaborative skills	Collaborative skills
	Transferable skills	Transferable skills	Transferable skills
	Networking skills	Networking skills	Networking skills
	Other	Other	Other
	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable
	If “Other”, please specify.	If “Other”, please specify.	If “Other”, please specify.

13. To what extent do you believe that your international mobility, intersectoral mobility, and/or interdisciplinary experiences have enhanced your employability and career opportunities?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To no extent	I don't know	Not applicable
Intersectoral						
International						
Interdisciplinary						

14. Any further comments?

Answer: Free text box.

15. Supervision - Did you have a single supervisor or a team of supervisors for your PhD research?

- One supervisor
- A supervisory team
- Other, explain

a. If Other, please specify.

Answer: Free text box.

16. If you had a supervisory team, how many supervisors did you have concurrently during your PhD research?

Scroll down menu: (a) 2, (b) 2-4, (c) other (free text)

a. If Other, please specify.

Answer: Free text box.

b. CONDITIONAL - if answer to question 12 is b or c.

If you had a supervisory team, in how many different scientific disciplines were the supervisors specialized?

Answer: Discrete values between 1 and 15

17. How were the supervision arrangements formalised between you and your supervisor(s)?

Answer only one column, i.e., whichever is applicable to you.

MSCA PhD researcher	Non-MSCA PhD researcher
<input type="checkbox"/> Through a document signed by the supervisor(s) and PhD researcher	<input type="checkbox"/> Through a document signed by the supervisor(s) and PhD researcher
<input type="checkbox"/> Through a written but not signed document	<input type="checkbox"/> Through a written but not signed document
<input type="checkbox"/> Through an oral agreement	<input type="checkbox"/> Through an oral agreement
<input type="checkbox"/> There was no supervision agreement between the supervisor(s) and PhD researcher	<input type="checkbox"/> There was no supervision agreement between the supervisor(s) and PhD researcher

18. How often did you meet with your supervisor(s) to discuss your research progress during your PhD?

Answer only one column, i.e., whichever is applicable to you.

MSCA PhD researcher	Non-MSCA PhD researcher
<input type="checkbox"/> Daily	<input type="checkbox"/> Daily
<input type="checkbox"/> Twice a week	<input type="checkbox"/> Twice a week
<input type="checkbox"/> Weekly	<input type="checkbox"/> Weekly
<input type="checkbox"/> Every two weeks	<input type="checkbox"/> Every two weeks
<input type="checkbox"/> Monthly	<input type="checkbox"/> Monthly
<input type="checkbox"/> Quarterly	<input type="checkbox"/> Quarterly
<input type="checkbox"/> When needed	<input type="checkbox"/> When needed

19. How do you rate your overall supervision experience during your PhD?

MSCA PhD researcher	Non-MSCA PhD researcher
<input type="checkbox"/> Excellent	<input type="checkbox"/> Excellent
<input type="checkbox"/> Very Good	<input type="checkbox"/> Very Good
<input type="checkbox"/> Good	<input type="checkbox"/> Good

<input type="checkbox"/> Average	<input type="checkbox"/> Average
<input type="checkbox"/> Below average	<input type="checkbox"/> Below average

20. During your PhD research, which type of trainings did you receive?
Rate them from 0 - 5 (0 being the least satisfactory and 5 the most satisfactory)?

	0	1	2	3	4	5	Not applicable
Networking							
Adaptability							
Interdisciplinary thinking							
Problem-solving							
Leadership							
Teamwork							
Negotiation and conflict resolution							
Ethical awareness							
Resilience and persistence							
Strategic thinking							
Policy understanding							
Public speaking and presentation							
Multilingual proficiency							
Project management							
Grant writing and fundraising							
Technical proficiency							
Innovation and creativity							
Data analysis and interpretation							
intersectoral knowledge transfer							
Other							

a. If "Other", please specify.
Answer: free-text box

21. As a PhD researcher, you received:

- An employment contract
- A PhD fellowship

- No funding
- Other

a. If Other, please specify.
Answer: Free text box

22. As a PhD researcher, you received:

Possible to select more than one option:

- Full social security coverage
- Partial social security coverage
- No social security coverage
- Pension rights
- No pension rights

23. To what extent was your salary/allowance sufficient to cover your living costs?

- To a very large extent
- To a large extent
- To some extent
- To little extent
- Not applicable

24. To what extent was the budget for training and research sufficient?

- To a very large extent
- To a large extent
- To some extent
- To little extent
- Not applicable

25. Was the length of your funding a concern in completing your PhD?

- Yes, significantly
- Yes, but not significantly
- No, it was not an issue
- Unable to assess

26. Which challenges have you encountered regarding your working conditions during your PhD?

Possible to select more than one option:

- No payment
- Late payment
- Unclear working contract and working conditions
- Low administrative support
- Challenging work-life balance
- Low family support
- Other

a. If Other, please specify.
Answer: Free text box

27. How extensively has your institution supported you in all administrative matters, and in what manner?

- To a very large extent
- To a large extent
- To some extent
- To little extent

a. If you have any comments:
Answer: free text box

28. How do you perceive the fairness of the recruitment process for PhD Graduates?

	Very fair	Fair	Rather fair	Not very fair	Not fair
Open					
Transparent					
Merit-based					
Impartial					
Equitable					

29. How long did it take you to find a job after the completion of your PhD?

- Less than 1 year
- 1 year
- Between 1 and 2 years
- More than 2 years"
- Not applicable

a. Please comment.
Answer: free-text box

b. To which extent was your job related to your training?

- To a very large extent
- To a large extent
- To some extent
- To No extent

c. CONDITIONAL if answer is a, b or c
Was the employment you found, after completing your PhD, at:

- Your PhD recruiting institution
- Your PhD awarding institution
- One of the institutions you collaborated with during your PhD studies
- An organisation not linked to your PhD studies
- Other

d. If Other, please specify.
Answer: Free text box.

e. Was the employment you found after completing your PhD, in:

- The academic sector
- The non-academic sector

30. What were the biggest challenges that you faced during your PhD?

Add check boxes (multiple choices possible)

- Research direction
- Interdisciplinary work
- Supervisor relationship
- Isolation
- Stress and mental health
- Networking
- Publication pressure
- Skill development
- Work-life balance
- Administrative burden
- Career uncertainty
- Language barriers
- Mobility
- Funding (securing adequate funding for research and living expenses)
- Research challenges (dealing with experimental failures, data collection issues, or unexpected research results)

31. What are the main challenges you faced during preparation for your post-PhD career, and what suggestions do you have to help reduce these challenges?

Answer: Free text

32. In your opinion, what improvements should be made in doctoral education in the coming years?

Answer: Free text